

International Rice Testing Program insect nurseries for 1976

Entomologists met during the 1976 International Rice Research Conference to discuss plans for the international program of screening for resistance to insect pests. They decided that the methodology for the 1975 brown planthopper and gall midge nurseries will remain the same in 1976 except for a few changes in the evaluation procedure and the check varieties, and the addition of new test locations.

A new nursery for stem borer evaluation will be initiated in 1976. Tentative plans were made for testing about 50 lines from six countries in Africa (at the International Institute for Tropical Agriculture), Korea, Thailand, Indonesia, Bangladesh, Sri Lanka, India, Iran, Egypt, and elsewhere.

Scientists who would like to grow and evaluate nursery sets for stem borer resistance are invited to request the sets directly from the International Rice Testing Program, IRRI.

Resistance of IR2070-4143-9 to rice whorl maggot

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Rice whorl maggot, *H. philippina*, was once considered a minor pest, but now it may be of major importance in the Philippines and in other ricegrowing countries in Asia. Whorl maggot attacks the rice plant at early stages, up to 40 days after transplanting. The symptoms of damage are whitish discolorations of the leaf margin and small holes on the leaf surface caused by the feeding of the larvae before leaf emergence from the whorl.

Field screening of rice varieties for whorl maggot resistance was initiated at IRRI in 1972. Since then about 20,000 rices have been screened. Several of the varieties were moderately resistant, but most were highly susceptible. The test varieties were planted at a spacing of 25 x 25 cm in a single row.

Those that were damaged least were retested to confirm their resistance. For retesting, the rices were planted in 1-x 5-m plots, replicated four times. Plant reactions to the pest were evaluated at the peak of damage from 25 to 30 days after transplanting, using standard scoring (0-9) by visual observation on a row basis. Among the rices tested, only the line IR2070-414-3-9 (CR94-13/IR20) showed a high level of resistance.

Greenhouse studies of the mechanisms of resistance revealed that resistance is

Yield performance of some gall midge-resistant cultures in field trials in Karnataka, India

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The rice gall midge is a serious pest of the first kharif crop in the coastal districts (South Kanara and North Kanara) of Karnataka. The damage was quite severe in 1974, and yield losses were as high as 25,000 tons in South Kanara alone, where 100,000 ha of rice is cultivated as kharif paddy. The high-yielding varieties Jaya, Sona, IR20, Vani, and Madhu are popular in the State, but they are not resistant to gall midge. In recent years, the pest has damaged crops even in the inland districts. Gall midge incidence was high in the summer of 1975 at Mandya. The number of galls per square meter recorded in a variety trial (49 entries) ranged from 10.2 for RP 268-42-3-2 to 65.6 for RP 545-73-3-5, with a mean of 24.6 ± 1.8 .

Since 1970, varieties have been screened for gall midge resistance at

mostly due to antibiosis. Plant dissection indicated few survivors on the resistant variety; those that survived were smaller than those reared on TN1. Further investigation of the sources of resistance in the field indicated that resistance comes from the parents (R 94-13 and IR20), both of which have moderate resistance. We are attempting to increase the level of resistance by making diallele crosses of moderately resistant parents. To locate additional resistant sources, we are evaluating the world collection.

Mangalore. Crossing of resistant donors with semidwarf high yielders has several potential F₄ progeny at Mandya/Mangalore. The table shows the merits of three resistant cultures identified at Mangalore from 1973 to 1975.

RPW6-13 was released in 1975 as Vikram in Karnataka. Experiments conducted from 1973 to 1975 reveal that RPW6-15 and CR93-4-2 exhibit yields significantly higher than those of Vikram. RPW6-15 is practically immune to the insect damage. CR93-4-2 is by far the best yielder and is also very early. It is superior to Vikram in gall midge resistance, but its grain is coarse. Since coarse grain is desired in the coastal areas (for parboiling), CR93-4-2 should be well accepted, especially in view of its high yield and better resistance.

These cultures have been registered for minikit trials in Karnataka during kharif 1976. Either RPW6-15 or CR93-4-2 is expected to be a good substitute for Vikram for better yield and resistance.

Yield performance of gall-midge-resistant cultures (av. of 3 years, 1973-1975). University of Agricultural Sciences, Hebbal, Bangalore, Karnataka, India.

Culture	Parents	Yield (t/ha)	Duration (days)	Galls (no./sq m)	Grain type
RPW6-13	IR8/Siam 29	3.6	136	7.09	long, bold
RPW6-15	IR8/Siam 29	4.1	133	0.04	long, bold
CR93-4-2	CR55-13/IR8	4.5	127	3.83	short, bold
Jaya		3.8	131	36.72	long, bold